

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

Toolkit Content and Updates (1st update)

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biorural.eu

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Executive Summary

The BioRural Toolkit is the central output of the BioRural project, designed to consolidate, present, and disseminate all project results in a structured and user-friendly format. Its main objective is to provide open access to all the bioeconomy knowledge and information collected and generated throughout the project, while fostering interaction and collaboration among rural stakeholders involved in the bioeconomy.

Available online at <https://biorural-toolkit.eu>, the Toolkit serves as both a knowledge repository and a collaboration platform. It enables users to explore factsheets, rural bioeconomy inventories, success stories, tutorials, business models, policy guidelines, and more. The platform encourages the exchange of experiences, co-creation of ideas, and formation of partnerships aimed at promoting sustainable, bio-based solutions tailored to rural needs.

Launched in month 6 of the BioRural project, the Toolkit was developed and maintained by the IUNG Team, who continuously monitored user engagement and feedback. This ongoing evaluation allowed for iterative improvements to its structure, functionality, and content, ensuring ease of use and practical relevance for its users.

Deliverable 4.3 describes the final version of BioRural Toolkit. It explores the toolkit's functionalities, its latest updates, and performance metrics. Chapter 1 provides an introduction with general information about the Toolkit. Chapter 2 presents the structure and content updates introduced separately for each category of material: Factsheets, Bioeconomy Inventory, Success stories, Online tutorials, Ideas and bioeconomy opportunities, Practice abstracts, Business Blueprints, and Policy and Research. Chapter 3 discusses the Interactive Network Map and functionalities available to registered and non-registered users, while chapter 4 is devoted to Geoportal. Chapter 5 covers the Privacy Policy and Terms and Conditions for toolkit users. Chapter 6 briefly presents the performance metrics of the Toolkit. In chapter 7, there are presented conclusions and further plans regarding the Toolkit.

The Toolkit is designed to remain a living platform. To ensure its long-term accessibility and continued evolution answering to the current needs of bioeconomy stakeholders, its development and maintenance will be carried forward under the thERBN project (January 2025 – December 2027). Additionally, with the aim to sustain the impact of BioRural results and further contribute to empowering rural actors, accelerating the adoption of bio-based practices, and fostering innovation across Europe's rural areas, the BioRural Toolkit has been connected with the EU-FarmBook Platform.

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1 Introduction

BioRural Toolkit is the main tool developed by BioRural, presenting all the project results. The aim of the Toolkit is to serve as a one-stop web-based tool providing access to the results and facilitating the use of information/knowledge collected and generated in the course of the project. It is also meant to enable interaction between rural actors, providing the platform to communicate, exchange experience and knowledge, and seek collaborations in the chosen fields of bioeconomy, thus supporting wider application of bio-based solutions in rural areas.

The toolkit can be found under the link: <https://biorural-toolkit.eu/>. Since its launch in M6, the IUNG Team responsible for the development and maintenance of the Toolkit had closely monitored its usage and collected feedback in order to update, when necessary, the structure and functionalities to enhance its attractiveness, ensure it is user friendly and to keep the content updated. Information regarding the previous steps of Toolkit development, its design and specifications can be found in deliverables: D4.1 Toolkit Design and System Requirements and D4.2 Toolkit Content and Updates.

The BioRural Toolkit is now available in its final version developed under BioRural project. To ensure open access to the collected materials and keep them updated and relevant for the ERBN community and other interested users, decision was made to continue its development within thERBN project (Jan 2025- Dec 2027).

2 BioRural Toolkit Structure and contents

The structure of BioRural Toolkit has been designed to fulfil the main purpose of this online tool – to provide access to the material collected in the course of the BioRural project implementation, through a user-friendly, intuitive interface, and to facilitate contact and collaboration of its users within the created networks.

Since the publication of Deliverable 4.2 in M13, no major changes have been made to the general layout of the BioRural Toolkit home page. It consists of categories presenting the collected and generated material on bio-based solutions in an organized way (Figure 1, on the right), and an interactive map showing the location of all the registered users (Figure 1, on the left). This layout corresponds with the main principle of the tool – to provide and facilitate the exchange of knowledge. Under the map, there is information about the financing, as well as Privacy policy and Terms and conditions for Toolkit users.

Figure 1. Layout of the BioRural Toolkit homepage

The layout presents the categories of material that correspond to those listed in WP4, T4.1 in a clear and explicit way, namely:

- (i) Factsheets of the rural Bioeconomy current status at national, regional and EU level □ **Factsheets**
- (ii) An inventory of selected research results (papers and projects), commercial bio-based solutions and funding opportunities □ **Bioeconomy inventories**
- (iii) The success stories' main characteristics combined with audio-visual material □ **Success stories**
- (iv) Knowledge sharing workshops recordings □ **Online tutorials**
- (v) Outcomes of capacity building workshops □ **Ideas and collaboration opportunities**
- (vi) **Practice abstracts**
- (vii) Rural development blueprints □ **Business blueprints**
- (viii) Policy and research guidelines □ **Policy and research**

The central button with project logo provides a link to BioRural project website.

The format of files included within each category and method of presentation of its contents has been adjusted to the specificity of the material. The file formats include: Portable Document Format (PDF), Video file formats (MP4), and graphics (.jpg, .png). All the above file formats have been chosen due to their widely accepted standards and widespread use among the Internet users.

The Toolkit is fully responsive, providing an optimal viewing and interaction experience across various devices. Figure 2 below presents the layout adjusted to the mobile phone screens. The homepage presents the Interactive

Network Map (picture on the left) (described further in chapter 3). The circled button provides access to the tiles presenting respective categories of material.

Figure 2. Layout of the BioRural Toolkit homepage adjusted to mobile phone screens

2.1 Factsheets

The BioRural factsheets aim to provide detailed information on specific bioeconomy topics and their status in a quick and easily digestible way for all stakeholders. **For the creation of factsheets, input was initially drawn and populated from the results of T1.1 Current Bioeconomy Status in Europe (M1-M6)** [Leader: CErTH; Partners: All].

For ease of access, it was decided to divide the tile into three tabs: EU factsheets, National Factsheets, and Regional factsheets that present area-specific content in the form of factsheets (PDF) available for downloading. The National Factsheets consist of reports on bioeconomy status in all 14 project partner countries. The categorization into EU/National/Regional scope was included in the filtering options built in the search engine. Filtering is also possible based on keywords provided by the user (see Figure 3).

The screenshot displays the BioRural search interface. At the top, there are three filter dropdowns: 'Filter by type' (set to 'Select your option'), 'Filter by subtype' (set to 'Select your option'), and 'Filter by projects' (set to 'BioRural'). Below these is a search bar. The main area shows six factsheet tiles, each with a title, subtitle, and a BioRural logo in the top right corner. A red circle highlights the BioRural logo in the top right corner of the first tile, 'EU Aquaculture: Status and Perspective'.

Title	Subtitle	Image Description
EU Aquaculture: Status and Perspective	EU factsheet	Aerial view of several circular aquaculture ponds in a body of water.
Biomass Logistics - Supply Chains	EU factsheet	A blue tractor with a log loader in a forest, carrying a large log.
Solid Biofuels production	EU factsheet	A bar chart showing energy production in Mtoe across various countries.
Recovery of by-products from agri-food industries ...	National factsheet	Hands holding soil and organic waste, including a pumpkin.
Manure potential in EU	EU factsheet	Two black and white cows in a green field.
Small-scale biorefining solutions	EU factsheet	A diagram of a biorefining process showing a glass cover, biogas storage, and zones for fluid, sludge, and mixing.

Figure 3. Filtering options of items presented in the Factsheets inventory include document type, subtype (geographical scope), project, and keywords

Since it was decided that the BioRural Toolkit will be further supported and developed by the ERBN project, a need appeared to distinguish the material collected and generated by each project as well. Therefore the option of filtering by project affiliation was added to the search engine. The origin of each item is indicated on the respective tile in the right top corner (Figure 3, circled in red).

The Factsheets are prepared following a unified methodology and data presentation in order to facilitate the interpretation, analysis and comparison of the collected information. Each factsheet presents information arranged in three sections: an overview, details, and a gallery of images, as presented in Figure 4, and can be downloaded in PDF format.

Figure 4. Layout of a factsheet based on example of "Circular Bioeconomy in Europe"

2.2 Rural Bioeconomy inventories

The BioRural inventory aims to provide stakeholders with an easily searchable database/repository of rural bioeconomy research results: Scientific Papers and Research projects, Commercial bio-based solutions, and Funding opportunities. The search engine allows for filtering the items in the inventory based on the category as well as bioeconomy themes, keywords inserted by the user, and projects that collected the material for the Toolkit.

Figure 5. Items collected in the bioeconomy inventories

The main input for this category has been provided from T4.2: BioRural Toolkit Development, Updates and Maintenance (M4-M36) [Leader: IUNG; Partners: All]. Each partner has contributed to the completion of this Task with material relevant for the implementation of circular bio-based solutions in European rural areas (concerning the geographic scope of the project partner country, the whole consortium, or EU in general). Thanks to the joint efforts, the KPI set for this Task has been reached and now the specific categories consist of at least: 200 scientific papers, 50 research projects, 100 commercial bio-based solutions, and 50 financing tools (specific numbers provided in Chapter 6) identified as relevant for the implementation of circular bio-based solutions in rural areas. Each of the collected items are described using the layout that presents information adjusted to the specificity of a given category and, at the same time, allows for presenting all the solutions in a unified manner, e.g. containing visual materials, short description, contact information of the author/provider of the paper/technology etc. Each solution is assigned to specific bioeconomy sector/sectors and provided a set of keywords, which facilitate the search for a desirable solution in the inventories.

The submission form for each of the four categories of solutions is presented in Annex II. Submission forms for bioeconomy inventories.

All submitted files undergo a screening process performed by the administrator of the Toolkit. After being submitted by registered users of the toolkit, all files have “private” status, which can be changed to “public” only be the toolkit administrator, who can view all files in the “administrator panel” presented in Figure 6. The administrator screens the files for the relevance of information provided as well as makes sure they provide

updated links to external sources, such as project websites, journal websites, contact information and additional materials. The administrator also makes sure that for all of the information presented on the Platform, a source is indicated.

Figure 6. Files submitted by registered toolkit users, visible in the "admin panel" section

When choosing one of the displayed solutions, the user is presented with a static page containing detailed information as shown in Figure 7-10. On the left, there is an image of the solution, a project logo, or the first page of a paper, and a short description below – depending on the type of the solution, it may be an abstract of a publication, project abstract, or a short description in case of a commercial solution/financing tool. Information presented on the right is divided into three categories: (i) general information, e.g. keywords, project acronym, bioeconomy theme, (ii) information on the solution provider/author, contact details and external links to the publication/project/company website, and, optionally, (3) additional materials (if available) which can be downloaded by the user. In case of scientific publications, no additional materials are expected.

<h2>The digital revolution in the bioeconomy</h2>	Information	
	Keywords digitalization, digital tools, real-time, data, biotechnology, circular	
Bioeconomy theme food & agriculture, forestry & natural habitat, biomaterials		Provider/Source
The digital revolution in the bioeconomy Digitalisation is integral to the development of the bioeconomy. This may have disruptive effects, but it may also contribute to the sustainability of bioeconomy industries. The Nordic Region has an abundance of bioresources and conscious use and development of these hold great potential for regional and local development. Research into the effects of digitalisation on the bioeconomy suggests that digitalisation is fostering transparency across value chains and helps to monitor the compliance with given rules and standards. From a rural development perspective, increased use of digital technologies is expected to play a role in attracting a younger generation to farming and rural business start-ups. Digitalisation changes the path for diversifying traditional bioeconomy sectors and is transforming the bioeconomy into an increasingly multi and interdisciplinary skilled sector. The first dimension sees the use of digital tools as a vehicle for precision-use and monitoring. For example, real-time monitoring of farming practices such as crops and livestock and brings added value through saved time and costs. Similarly, in the forestry sector, monitoring can bring added value by generating data, optimising the preservation and use of forest ecosystem services. The second dimension pertains to the bioeconomy as part of the circular economy, where data may aid the improvement of value chains; to reuse, recycle and repair. Data analysis generated from digitalisation in, for example, biorefineries or bio-based manufacturing may help identify new products emerging from what was previously defined as waste.		
Name of the author Nordic Council of Ministers		Journal Nordic Council of Ministers
< Official website/DOI		✉ Contact
		Date of publication 20/05/2020

Figure 7 Tab design for scientific papers.

<h2>Promoting the penetration of agrobiomass heating in European rural areas</h2>	Information	
	Acronym AgroBioHeat	Keywords Bioenergy, rural, agrobiomass, agricultural residues agroindustry byproducts, energy crops, heating,
Bioeconomy theme food & agriculture, bioenergy		Provider/Source
Promoting the penetration of agrobiomass heating in European rural areas AgroBioHeat project aims to produce a mass deployment of improved and market ready agrobiomass heating solutions in Europe. Agrobiomass is a large, under-exploited and indigenous resource, which can support the achievement of the European Energy and Climate targets, while promoting rural development and circular economy. Actions are carried mainly in 6 European countries: Greece, Spain, France, Romania, Croatia and Ukraine. Project is centred in bioenergy solutions for heating in small and medium scale applications. Actions of research carried on efficiency of boilers, and CSA actions on accompaniment, roadmaps, advocacy and divulgation of best practices and success cases.		
Funding source european		Budget 2 998 043
Name of the coordinator CERTH - The Centre for Research & Technology, Hellas		
✉ Contact	< Official website/DOI	Project duration
Material		
🎧 Audio-Visual Materials		📄 Additional Materials

Figure 8. Tab design for research projects

<p>Maize cob selector - maize residues (cobs) as a source of electricity, heat and fertilizers</p> <p>Power Maize is an innovative system of technology for obtaining agricultural production residues - maize cob cores. Many years of experience and unique technology allow us to use waste from maize production as a high-energy source of energy. The collecting machine offered by the collection is fully compatible with RES. Various forms of cooperation are possible depending on the individual needs of our clients. Our mission is to provide clean energy using waste for the sake of the environment. We save money and the planet.</p>	Information		
	Location Poland	Keywords maize cob, agricultural residues, heating, renewable energy	
	Bioeconomy theme food & agriculture, bioenergy		
	Provider/Source		
	Funding source Private		
	Name of the company POWER MAIZE sp z o.o.		
	← Official website/DOI	✉ Contact	
Material			
📺 Audio-Visual Materials		↓ Additional Materials	

Figure 9. Tab design for commercial solutions

<p>Investments contributing to environmental and climate protection</p> <p>The aid may be applied for by a farmer (natural person, legal person, organisational unit without legal personality, partners in a civil partnership carrying out agricultural activities as part of a civil partnership) or a group of farmers. The catalogue of investments includes, among others:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - construction or reconstruction of slabs for the collection and storage of solid natural fertilisers, as well as tanks for the storage of liquid natural fertilisers; - construction or purchase of tanks and equipment for improving water management; - purchase of computer programmes, applications, equipment to support and optimise the production decision-making process; - purchase of agricultural machinery and equipment for e.g. application of mineral or natural fertilisers, compost, digestion products; plant protection; sowing; soil cultivation; cultivation and harvesting of biomass from permanent grassland. <p>In the case of a group of farmers, support may only be granted for the purchase of agricultural machinery or equipment or for intangible investments, such as the acquisition of licences.</p>	Information		
	Location Poland	Keywords CAP, Strategic Plan, agricultural machinery and equipment	
	Bioeconomy theme food & agr culture		
	Provider/Source		
	Funding source National	Type of funding investment in infrastructure	Budget 200 000 PLN per applicant
	Name of the financing institution Agencja Restrukturyzacji i Modernizacji Rolnictwa		
	← Official website	✉ Contact	Financing period 24/10/2024 - 24/10/2024
Material			
📺 Audio-Visual Materials		↓ Additional Materials	

Figure 10. Tab design for financing tools

2.3 BioRural Success stories

The input for this category has been provided by T2.4 Identification of success stories in each Rural Bioeconomy Platform (M10-M36) [Leader: ICO; Partners: All].

The BioRural success stories' main characteristics combined with audio-visual material are presented in the Toolkit. The aim of these is to provide an easily accessible overview of each success story, showcasing their innovativeness and factors that drove their development. The success stories are divided along the five bioeconomy themes: Food & agriculture, Forestry & natural habitat, Aquatic & water systems, Bioenergy, Biomaterials (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Tiles presenting uploaded success stories

Throughout the course of the project, new success stories have been identified by project partners and uploaded on the Toolkit, in addition to the 8 original success stories provided at the launch of the platform.

The layout of success story page has not changed - each of them presents the main information regarding the presented case: a photo and a short description on the left, general information and contact details with a video presenting the solution on the right. A new feature has been added to facilitate sharing the success story on social media – the new function can be seen below in Figure 12 (circled in red).

The screenshot displays a webpage for MicrobePlus. On the left, there is a white plastic jug of 'BACTO GRALL BIOSTIMULATOR'. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column features a blue header 'MicrobePlus - Biological solutions provided by nature' followed by several paragraphs of text describing the product's benefits and testing. The right column has a blue header 'Information' and contains a table with details like 'Bioeconomy theme: food & agriculture', 'Date founded: 01/01/2022', and 'Funding sources: public, market, private'. Below this is a 'Share it' section with social media icons for Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter, which are circled in red. A 'Why is it an innovative/circular bioeconomy success story:' section follows, containing three bullet points. At the bottom, there is a 'Video' section with a 'Copy link' button and a video player showing a woman in a field.

Figure 12. Example of a static page presenting a success story of the Polish start-up company MicrobePlus

2.4 Online Knowledge Exchange Tutorials

Work package 3 (T.3.1 Online knowledge exchange on Bioeconomy (M1-M36) [Leader: UL; Partners: CERTH, AU, AlgEn, GGP, UC, IUNG, LLU, NP] provided input for the inventory of the Online Knowledge Exchange Tutorials. A series of five EU online workshops with different groups of stakeholders and devoted to different bioeconomy themes have been organized and recorded with the aim to share and disseminate knowledge on bio-based solutions. Each workshop held over the course of 3 days covered lectures/discussions on ‘basic concept(s), technical principles,’ ‘showcase of good practices, factors of success’ and ‘cross-cutting themes.’ On each day, 5-6 lectures/discussions of around 15 minutes were conducted. The recordings, along with additional educational material, are available to users categorized according to the bioeconomy themes under:

- Agriculture and food
- Forestry and natural habitats
- Aquatic and water systems
- Bioenergy
- Biomaterials

Key and easily accessible bioeconomy knowledge are available for all stakeholders through 90+ stand-alone tutorials, 15 minutes each, presented by experts covering technical principles, case studies and cross cutting themes for all bioeconomy themes.

Figure 13. Online tutorials repository

Inside each of the circled categories (Figure 13) there are separate tiles for each lecture/presentation delivered at the workshop. They include information about the author (name and photo, short bio), about the lecture (title, synopsis, presentation in PDF) and the video link to the recording of a lecture published on BioRural YouTube channel (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Examples of presentations delivered during the Forestry and habitats workshop (March 2024)

With the aim to enrich the Toolkit with relevant materials whenever possible, the BioRural team decided to add other sources of information produced by project partners that Toolkit users may benefit from – hence the addition of two extra tiles: Innovation and Entrepreneurship, and Bioeconomy educational resources (bottom of Figure 13). The former presents discussions on innovation in circular bioeconomy in a similar layout to previous workshops

(Figure 15), the latter provides a link to an outside resource of e-learning courses developed in the framework of RELIEF project (Figure 16).

Figure 15. Examples of presentations from the Innovation and Entrepreneurship workshop

RELIEF has developed an e-learning platform for HEIs students and farming practitioners to advance the bioeconomy in farming and agriculture. The learning resources are a-synchronous and available in 5 languages for self-training and networking to support the long-term sustainability of farming enterprises. It provides 45 courses covering main topics including: Digital Technologies & AI, Horizontal, Controlled Environment Agriculture, Bio and Circular Economy, and Agricultural Sustainability.

Figure 16. Tab with E-learning courses prepared by the RELIEF project

2.5 Ideas and collaboration opportunities

The aim of this section was to synthesize and provide key bioeconomy educational material originating out of the BioRural's 42 national capacity building workshops. The input for this category has been provided by T3.2 Generation of interactive and multi-actor innovation at national level (M7-M24). The materials collected under this category present the most relevant ideas for bioeconomy solutions selected from all partner countries and beyond, who participated in the Bioeconomy Challenge organised in the framework of Task 3.3 Fostering cross-border collaboration M16-36 [Leader: ICO, Partners: All]. This category has also been designed with the aim to create a

platform for presenting collaboration opportunities/seek partners for development of bioeconomy ideas as well as inspire users .

Figure 17. Tiles presenting innovative bioeconomy ideas

The layout for presentation of ideas uploaded to the Toolkit includes information about the author/producer/ company developing the solution, contact details, description of the product or technology and, if relevant, information about seeking collaboration or development opportunities (Figure 18).

PURE PIGMENT

Information

Name Adrian Misztal	Pure Pigment sp. z o.o.
← Official website	✉ Contact
Bioeconomy theme Food and agriculture, Biomaterials	Level Poland
Additional information ← Link	Share it f in X

Organic, chemically unmodified pigments for biopolymers from agri-food industry waste

Pure Pigment is a startup that develops a breakthrough technology that allows for the double use of agri-food waste. Our solution allows you to obtain natural pigments from waste and then transform the same material into a biopolymer. The flagship project of the company is ECOMasterbatch - a coloring granulate for biodegradable plastics with organic pigment. Acting in the spirit of a circular economy, we minimize the consumption of raw materials, while at the same time contributing to the global efforts to decarbonize the industry. Our technology is the answer to the questions posed in the UN 2030 Agenda regarding sustainable development.

Looking for collaboration

We are looking for:

Suppliers of waste from fruit and vegetable processing

A company or person specializing in the production of biopolymers that would be interested in testing the product or establishing business cooperation

Investors ready to invest in small-scale pigment production and R&D research in the area of pigments and biopolymers ✉ Send a message

Figure 18. Layout of bioeconomy idea - example of Pure Pigment from Poland

The submission form for bioeconomy ideas and collaboration opportunities is presented in Annex IV.

2.6 Practice abstracts

The inventory of practice abstracts has been fed with materials prepared by the project partners and divided into the five categories of bioeconomy themes. All the practice abstracts have been prepared in line with the EIP-AGRI common format and are available for downloading. The material has been developed within T5.1 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (M1-M36) [Leader: FSH; Partners: All].

Figure 19. Page presenting short description of the content to be expected in the category of practice abstracts

2.7 Business Blueprints

The inventory of Business Blueprints presents the result of Task 5.3 Business models for resilience and circularity (M1-M36) [Leader: FSH; Partners All]. It offers business model blueprints for rural development in each of the five bioeconomy themes, based on the Triple layer Business Model Canvas. The five panels with blueprints are presented in Figure 20. They can be viewed online or downloaded in PDF format.

Business model blueprints developed for five bioeconomy themes relying upon the analytical framework for circular business model innovation

Figure 20. Page presenting short description of the content to be expected in the category of business blueprints

2.8 Policy and research

The Policy and Research category present the results of Task 3.4 Policy guidelines for rural Bioeconomy development in M24-M36 [Leader: CERN; Partners: All]. The recommendations are divided into horizontal and specific policy briefs and can be previewed or downloaded as a PDF file.

The **BioRural Policy Briefs** present key policy recommendations to support national and EU decision-makers in advancing the circular bioeconomy. Grounded in extensive evidence from BioRural activities, the briefs identify policy gaps through a triangulated approach comparing grassroots needs, institutional frameworks, and solution readiness. They aim to equip policymakers and rural stakeholders with practical tools to drive a more inclusive and sustainable rural bioeconomy in Europe.

Figure 21. Page presenting BioRural Policy Briefs with a short description of the content

3 Interactive Network Map

The aim of the interactive network map is to provide an online space facilitating interaction and collaboration between bioeconomy stakeholders – the ERBN members – identified in all tasks and work packages, in particular those identified in Task 2.1, who have been invited to register on the toolkit. The aim of reaching 400 stakeholders registered to the toolkit by the end of the project has been realised - at the moment of submission of this deliverable, there are 590 registered Toolkit users. The registration form is presented in Annex V.

The Interactive Network Map provides information about the registered stakeholders who gave their consent for being presented on the map (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Presentation of personal information is based upon the consent from the user (which can be revoked at any time)

The presented information include: (1) name, (2) affiliation/profession, (3) address, (4) area of activity, (5) bioeconomy theme, (6) description, (7) affiliated projects, (8) website address (Figure 23). The categories of information are not obligatory - each user can decide if and how much information they want to share. The users can search for a specific name/organization using the search engine (marked at the top of the map) or filter the stakeholders by type or bioeconomy theme (filtering options marked below the map). The filtering/search results are directly visible on the map and include the name and type of the stakeholder, bioeconomy theme, name and address of the institution and website address, if provided by the stakeholder. For registered users, they are available for downloading as .xls file (download button in the bottom right corner – available only).

Figure 23. Presentation of user information on the interactive map

The choice of stakeholder types comprises:

- Associations, clusters, NGOs
- Government and public administrations
- Private company/self-employed
- Research and education
- Other

The bioeconomy themes consist of:

- Aquatic/water systems
- Bioenergy
- Biomaterials
- Food/agriculture
- Forestry/natural habitats

3.1 User registration and additional functionalities

Apart from the basic personal information a stakeholder is required to provide in order to create an account, they have a possibility of adding a description of their activities, organization, work focus etc., providing contact information including a phone number and website address (Figure 24). The optional contact information consist also of social networks' profiles (Figure 25), which may facilitate creating collaboration networks, finding suitable partners for joint ventures or simply keeping up to date with the activities of other stakeholders in our area of interest.

Figure 24. Presentation of user profile (visible only to registered user)

Figure 25. Profile settings allowing for introduction of additional information such as social networks' profiles

Both the interactive map and the toolkit are accessible to non-registered users of the website. However, registration provides additional functionalities, such as storing files on the private account or adding files to the inventory (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Additional functionalities for registered users

Each registered user will be able to add items to the BioRural inventory using a designated online form. The suitable form containing questions relevant for the particular category of bio-based solution will appear upon selecting the category in the search tool. The forms used in each case are provided in Annexes I-IV.

All files submitted by the registered users will have the status of private files until accepted for publication by the administrator. Each user will be able to view and edit submitted files, as well as to check their publication status, as it is presented in Figure 27.

All the factsheets submitted for publishing on the Toolkit are visible both to the author and to the administrator of the Platform. The latter is responsible for screening the content before accepting it for publication. This process is described in more detail in section 2.2. The respective submission form for this type of material is presented in Annex II.

Figure 27. Files submitted to the inventory by a registered user, each with a different publication status

4 Geoportal

The interactive map presented in the homepage have been complemented with the Geoportal, which can be entered using the button in the bottom left corner. After opening the geoportal options (Figure 28) users can browse through different categories of geospatial information available for Europe to be displayed on the map. The information includes: (1) biodegradable municipal waste theoretical potential, (2) food waste theoretical potential, (3) forest theoretical potential, (4) manure theoretical potential, and (5) straw theoretical potential.

Figure 28. Geoportal presenting theoretical potential of biodegradable municipal waste in Europe

Apart from the visual modifications, the content presented in Geoportal has remained unchanged.

5 Privacy policy / Terms and Conditions

The Privacy Policy and Terms and Conditions of the BioRural Toolkit outline the rights and responsibilities of both the Toolkit and its users. As BioRural is committed to being transparent and ensuring that the privacy of its users is always protected, the Privacy Policy is detailing how user data is collected, used, stored, and protected, in compliance with relevant data protection laws. The BioRural Privacy Policy in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) governs personal information collection and usage covering the following:

- Information about the administrator of collected data, Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation – State Research Institute in Puławy, Poland.
- Categories of personal data collected from registered and non-registered Toolkit Users
- Purpose for personal data processing
- Legal basis for data processing
- Reminds about the rights of BioRural Toolkit users under the GDPR

The full text of the BioRural Toolkit Privacy Policy is presented in Annex VI.

The Terms and Conditions set the rules for using the Toolkit, outline acceptable behavior, limitations of liability, and dispute resolution processes. The document informs its users about:

- Toolkit License
- Prohibited activity
- Right to terminate user account
- Ownership of the published content
- Right to update or modify terms of use
- Disclaimer of Warranty
- Disclaimer of Liability
- Governing law the Toolkit and its users are subjected to
- Privacy Policy compliant with GDPR

The full text of Terms and conditions of BioRural Toolkit use is presented in Annex VII.

Both Terms and conditions and Privacy Policy have not changed and can be accessed during new users registration from the user registration form, and anytime from the homepage of the BioRural Toolkit.

6 BioRural Toolkit performance metrics

In the last month of the project implementation (August '25), the BioRural Toolkit had 590 registered users. As many as 325 new users registered since D4.2 (M13).

When it comes to toolkit users in general (registered and non-registered), the majority visited the platform using a direct link: placed on promotional materials, online news items or articles about the toolkit etc., which proves successful the promotional initiatives carried out by the project consortium. The second most numerous channel was organic search, meaning that users have heard about the platform or searched for a certain content online which resulted in accessing the toolkit. It is a relevant indicator for the reliability and visibility of the Toolkit since the organic search results are based on factors like relevance, quality, and authority of the webpage's content, as well as the quality of backlinks provided on the website. Almost as many users visited the toolkit through a referral from another online source, which means the Toolkit has been recognized and promoted by other source.

Organic social traffic has the lowest score and refers to all social media activity not paid for through advertising. It encompasses the content and interactions created on social media platforms without using paid promotional tools. It reflects the effect of promotional efforts and activities that BioRural carried out to engage with its audience on social media. The numbers discussed are presented in Figure 29 and Figure 30 below.

Figure 29. Primary channels used to access the BioRural Toolkit in the period from M13 to M36

First user prim...Channel Group) +		↓ Total users	New users	Returning users
Total		2,937 100% of total	2,863 100% of total	625 100% of total
1	Direct	2,003 (68.2%)	1,930 (67.41%)	438 (70.08%)
2	Organic Search	452 (15.39%)	452 (15.79%)	75 (12%)
3	Referral	364 (12.39%)	364 (12.71%)	104 (16.64%)
4	Organic Social	117 (3.98%)	117 (4.09%)	8 (1.28%)

Figure 30. Number of total, new, and returning users in the period from M13 to M36 based on primary channels

When it comes to demographic details, most of the Toolkit visitors come from United States: over 17% of both new and active users. However, the highest number of engaged sessions was recorded from Poland (68.4% engagement rate) Portugal (65.62%), and Slovenia (62.53%).

Country ▾		+	↓	Active users	New users	Engaged sessions	Engagement rate
Total				2,935 100% of total	2,863 100% of total	4,009 100% of total	56.36% Avg 0%
1	United States			501 (17.07%)	493 (17.22%)	53 (1.32%)	10.5%
2	Portugal			199 (6.78%)	197 (6.88%)	250 (6.24%)	65.62%
3	Spain			193 (6.58%)	191 (6.67%)	361 (9%)	61.71%
4	Greece			192 (6.54%)	186 (6.5%)	326 (8.13%)	50.54%
5	Netherlands			191 (6.51%)	187 (6.53%)	130 (3.24%)	55.32%
6	Poland			153 (5.21%)	146 (5.1%)	1,186 (29.58%)	68.4%
7	Germany			151 (5.14%)	150 (5.24%)	139 (3.47%)	54.3%
8	France			143 (4.87%)	139 (4.86%)	144 (3.59%)	52.75%
9	Ireland			126 (4.29%)	123 (4.3%)	75 (1.87%)	57.25%
10	Slovenia			117 (3.99%)	114 (3.98%)	252 (6.29%)	62.53%

Figure 31. Number of active and new users recorded in the period from M13 to M36 based on 10 most represented countries

The traffic on the Toolkit and interest in specific content varied over time, which has been caused both by different timeline for material upload in specific categories as well as different project events where the Toolkit was promoted. Considering the last 90 days as many as 564 new users visited the BioRural toolkit, while 136 of them were returning to the platform for at least second or more times, which suggests as many as 136 users found it interesting and useful to search and come back for more information (Figure 32). The traffic could have been enhanced by the Bioeconomy challenge final as well as the EuRCBC conference held at the beginning of May'25.

Figure 32. Number of users visiting the Toolkit throughout the period of 90 days (from May 1st, 2025 onwards)

Regarding the most visited pages, the top interest gained success stories (10.47%), then factsheets (9.1%), online tutorials (7.41%), and bioeconomy inventories (6.68%). The categories with no content at the time of measuring the traffic such as business blueprints and policy and research also recorded some visits (with short engagement time), which means this kind of material may be of interest to many stakeholders.

The uploaded material comprises 549 files to date (Figure 33), including: 38 factsheets, 48 success stories, 225 scientific papers, 71 research projects, 105 commercial biobased solutions, and 50 funding opportunities. These numbers are expected to grow as the Toolkit is open to external contributions from other EU projects as well as individuals, keeping in mind the overall goal to ensure access and facilitate exchange of relevant and current knowledge on circular bio-based solutions dedicated for rural areas.

Figure 33. Share of material from different categories uploaded on the BioRural Toolkit as of 08.08.2025

7 Conclusions

This document has presented the content and updates of the BioRural Toolkit. Updates and additional materials have been introduced to Factsheets, Bioeconomy inventories, Success stories, Online Tutorials, and Practice Abstracts, while new content has been uploaded to Ideas and collaboration opportunities, Business Blueprints, Policy and research.

The final form of the Toolkit is a result of joint efforts of the whole BioRural Consortium as well as feedback collected from ERBN stakeholders. Throughout the duration of the project, IUNG collaborated closely with all consortium partners to ensure the Toolkit remained current, interactive, and aligned with project objectives. Regular updates and structural enhancements were systematically applied to optimize the visibility and accessibility of the project's key actions and results, facilitate user engagement, and maintain ongoing stakeholder interest. Feedback has been also collected during T3.2 and 3.3 workshops from the Toolkit users, to validate the relevance of the content and make sure the information is easy to search and access.

The BioRural Toolkit is now in its final form which enables networking of stakeholders, provides the ground for wider application of bio-based solutions in rural areas allowing the transitions of rural areas from linear economy to circular bio-based economy, and which will support post-project sustainability of results. To this aim, BioRural Toolkit has been connected with the EU-FarmBook Platform, which serves as a central repository of knowledge, to strengthen the overall knowledge exchange ecosystem. The Toolkit will be also further maintained and developed in the framework of thERBN¹ project devoted to establishing a pan-European network for bioeconomy knowledge sharing.

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101182955>

8 Annex

8.1 Annex I. Submission form for Factsheets

HOME | MAŁGORZATA WYDRA | LOG OUT |

FACTSHEETS | SELECT TYPE | SELECT SUBTYPE

TITLE *

OVERVIEW *

NORMAL | B | I | U | |

8.2 Annex II. Submission forms for bioeconomy inventories

8.2.1 Submission form for scientific papers

The screenshot shows a web-based submission form for scientific papers. The form is set against a dark background with white text and input fields. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'HOME', 'MALGORZATA WYDRA', 'LOG OUT', and a language selector (UK flag). Below this, there are two dropdown menus: 'BIOECONOMY INVENTORIES' and 'SCIENTIFIC PAPERS'. The main form area contains several input fields and a list of themes. The fields are: 'ARTICLE TITLE *', 'SHORT DESCRIPTION *' (with a character count of 0/2000), 'KEYWORDS *', 'AUTHOR'S FULL NAME *', 'JOURNAL *', 'WEBSITE / DOI *', 'CONTACT *', and 'PUBLICATION DATE *' (with the date 14/07/2025). To the right of these fields is a section for 'BIOECONOMY THEME *' with five checkboxes: 'FOOD AND AGRICULTURE', 'FORESTRY AND NATURAL ENVIRONMENT', 'WATER SYSTEMS AND AQUACULTURE', 'BIOENERGY', and 'BIOMATERIALS'. At the bottom of the form, there is a section for 'PRODUCED BY: (OPTIONAL)' with two dashed boxes containing '+ ADD NEW PROJECT' and '+ ADD CUSTOM PROJECT'. A 'SAVE' button is located at the bottom right of the form.

HOME | MALGORZATA WYDRA | LOG OUT | UK

BIOECONOMY INVENTORIES | SCIENTIFIC PAPERS

ARTICLE TITLE *

SHORT DESCRIPTION * 0/2000

KEYWORDS *

AUTHOR'S FULL NAME *

JOURNAL *

WEBSITE / DOI *

CONTACT *

PUBLICATION DATE * 14/07/2025

BIOECONOMY THEME *

- FOOD AND AGRICULTURE
- FORESTRY AND NATURAL ENVIRONMENT
- WATER SYSTEMS AND AQUACULTURE
- BIOENERGY
- BIOMATERIALS

PRODUCED BY: (OPTIONAL)

+ ADD NEW PROJECT + ADD CUSTOM PROJECT

SAVE

8.2.2 Submission form for research projects

HOME | MALGORZATA WYDRA | LOG OUT |
BIOECONOMY INVENTORIES ▾
RESEARCH PROJECTS ▾

IMAGE GALLERY, MAX 3 * (BEST SIZE 3X2)

+

PROJECT TITLE *

SHORT DESCRIPTION *

0/2000

ACRONYM *

FUNDING SOURCE

European ▾

KEYWORDS *

COORDINATOR'S FULL NAME *

BUDGET *

BIOECONOMY THEME *

- FOOD AND AGRICULTURE
- FORESTRY AND NATURAL ENVIRONMENT
- WATER SYSTEMS AND AQUACULTURE
- BIOENERGY
- BIOMATERIALS

WEBSITE/DOI *

CONTACT *

PROJECT DURATION *

14/07/2025 - 14/07/2025

AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

Upload

PRODUCED BY: (OPTIONAL)

+ ADD NEW PROJECT

+ ADD CUSTOM PROJECT

SAVE

8.2.3 Submission form for commercial biobased solutions

HOME | MALGORZATA WYDRA | LOG OUT |

BIOECONOMY INVENTORIES ▾ COMMERCIAL BIO-BASED SOLUTIONS ▾

IMAGE GALLERY, MAX 3 * (BEST SIZE 3X2)

SOLUTION NAME *

SHORT DESCRIPTION * 0/2000

LOCATION * Global ▾ FUNDING SOURCE * European ▾

KEYWORDS *

COMPANY NAME *

WEBSITE/DOI *

CONTACT *

BIOECONOMY THEME *

- FOOD AND AGRICULTURE**
- FORESTRY AND NATURAL ENVIRONMENT**
- WATER SYSTEMS AND AQUACULTURE**
- BIOENERGY**
- BIOMATERIALS**

AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

 Upload

PRODUCED BY: (OPTIONAL)

+ ADD NEW PROJECT **+ ADD CUSTOM PROJECT**

 SAVE

8.2.4 Submission form for funding opportunities

HOME | MALGORZATA WYDRA | LOG OUT |

BIOECONOMY INVENTORIES ▾ FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES ▾

LOCATION: Global ▾ FUNDING SOURCE: European ▾ FUNDING TYPE: Direct ▾

KEYWORDS

BUDGET

FINANCING INSTITUTION NAME

WEBSITE/DOI

BIOECONOMY THEME *

- FOOD AND AGRICULTURE
- FORESTRY AND NATURAL ENVIRONMENT
- WATER SYSTEMS AND AQUACULTURE
- BIOENERGY
- BIOMATERIALS

CONTACT

FINANCING PERIOD: 14/07/2025 - 14/07/2025

AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

 Upload

PRODUCED BY: (OPTIONAL)

+ ADD NEW PROJECT + ADD CUSTOM PROJECT

 SAVE

8.3 Annex III. Submission form for success stories

SUCCESS STORIES ▾
HOME | MAŁGORZATA WYDRA | LOG OUT | ◀

TITLE *

LOGO *

+

IMAGE GALLERY, MAX 3 * (BEST SIZE 3X2)

+

VIDEO *

DESCRIPTION *

0/2000

WHY IS IT INNOVATIVE (MAXIMUM 6 POINTS) *

ADD NEW POINT
SAVE

BIOECONOMY THEME

- FOOD AND AGRICULTURE**
- FORESTRY AND NATURAL ENVIRONMENT**
- WATER SYSTEMS AND AQUACULTURE**
- BIOENERGY**
- BIOMATERIALS**

CONTACT

WEBSITE *

DATE FOUNDED *

14/07/2025

FUNDING SOURCE *

- PRIVATE**
- PUBLIC**
- MARKET**

PRODUCED BY: (OPTIONAL)

+ ADD NEW PROJECT

+ ADD CUSTOM PROJECT

🏠 SAVE

8.4 Annex IV. Submission form for Ideas and collaboration opportunities

ADD YOUR IDEA
HOME | MAŁGORZATA WYDRA | LOG OUT | |

LOGO/IMAGE *

+

IDEA TITLE *

DESCRIPTION *

0/2000

IF YOU ARE LOOKING FOR COLLABORATORS, PROVIDE MORE DETAILS

Team of innovators looking for suppliers of biomass, technology developer, IT specialist...

0/500

GEOGRAPHIC LEVEL *

Global

GEOGRAPHIC LEVEL *

Global

COMPANY/INSTITUTION NAME/IDEA ACRONYM/OTHER *

OFFICIAL WEBSITE *

CONTACT INFORMATION *

BIOECONOMY THEME *

- FOOD AND AGRICULTURE
- FORESTRY AND NATURAL ENVIRONMENT
- WATER SYSTEMS AND AQUACULTURE
- BIOENERGY
- BIOMATERIALS

MORE INFORMATION (UP TO 3 URLS):

Add your url...

Add

SAVE

8.5 Annex V. User registration form

REGISTER FOR THE BIORURAL TOOLKIT BELOW

Full name Required

John Doe

0/60

Organization/Profession

Bioeconomy company / Manager

Email Required

JohnDoe@domain.com

0/60

Password Required

Password

Confirm password Required

1/4 Next step →

REGISTER FOR THE BIORURAL TOOLKIT BELOW

Address Required **Country** Required

Pałac Czartoryskich, 8, Czartoryskich, Osiedle Cz Poland

You can correct the marker position by clicking on the map. You can also get your address from the map, but first you need to delete the current address and click outside the field.

← Previous step 2/4 Next step →

REGISTER FOR THE BIORURAL TOOLKIT BELOW

Here you can add projects you participate in (maximum 3).

Project name	Project link	ADD

← Previous step
3/4
Next step →

REGISTER FOR THE BIORURAL TOOLKIT BELOW

Stakeholder type Required

Private company/self employed ▼

Bioeconomy theme Required

- Food/agriculture
- Forestry/natural environment
- Water systems/aquatic
- Bioenergy
- Biomaterials

- I want my email to be visible to guests
- Visible on the map and open to sharing contact details
- I want to receive BioRural updates and newsletter

By creating an account you agree to our [Privacy policy](#) and [Terms and conditions](#).

← Previous step
4/4
Register
✎

8.6 Annex VI. Privacy policy

This privacy policy governs the use of your personal data by the BioRural project – this project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101060166.

NOTE: If you want information on how we process personal data via cookies on the BioRural Toolkit, you are kindly referred to our [Cookie Policy](#).

Referring to the content of Article 13 of the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of April 27, 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) - (OJ EU.L 119 of 04.05.2016, p. 1 and OJ EU.L 127 of 23.05.2018 p. 2, hereinafter the “Regulation”), the Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation – State Research Institute in Puławy informs as follows:

1. Who is responsible for the processing of your personal data?

1.1 The administrator of your personal data is the Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation – State Research Institute (IUNG-PIB) in Puławy (address: 8 Czartoryskich St., 24-100 Puławy, tel. 81 4786 700 or 800, e-mail: iung@iung.pulawy.pl).

Your personal data are processed in the framework of the BioRural project by IUNG-PIB and by Foodscale Hub, dissemination and communication partner of the BioRural project – this project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101060166. You can contact us via e-mail at toolkit@biorural.eu.

1.2 The personal data administrator reserves the right to modify, change or amend this Privacy Policy at its own discretion and from time to time. Such modifications, changes or amendments shall be communicated via the BioRural Toolkit. In case of questions or comments with regard to the modifications, changes or amendments, you can inform us by sending an e-mail to toolkit@biorural.eu.

1.3 The personal data administrator has appointed a data protection officer with whom you may contact in matters relating to data processing and the exercise of rights related to data processing, via e-mail at: iod@iung.pulawy.pl, or telephone number - 81 4786 738, or in writing, at the address indicated in Section 1.1

2. What categories of personal data do we process?

2.1 When you contact us via e-mail, telephone or Social Media Channels, we collect:

- the basic identity information you provide us with, such as name, e-mail address, postal address, telephone number, the company you work for, your function;
- the content of your communication and the technical details of the communication itself (with whom you correspond at our end, date and time, etc.);
- electronic identification data, such as IP address;
- publicly available information of your profile on Social Media Channels and any other personal data you choose to provide to us with.

2.2 Whenever you register at the BioRural Toolkit, we may collect:

- the basic identity information you provide us with, such as name, e-mail address, social media profiles, postal address, telephone number, the company you work for, projects you are involved in, stakeholder type and area of your activity, or any other information you choose to include in your profile description;

- your image if you decide to add it to your profile.

3. For what purpose do we use your personal data?

3.1 The personal data administrator processes your personal data to provide you in a personalized and efficient way with the information, products and/or services you request via the BioRural Toolkit, e-mail, telephone, etc.

3.2 The personal data administrator processes your personal data to communicate with you as a result of your approach via the BioRural Toolkit, e-mail, telephone or one of our Social Media Channels.

3.3 The personal data administrator processes your personal data to perform statistical analyses so that we may improve our products and services or develop new products and services.

3.4 The personal data administrator processes your personal data to comply with legal obligations or to comply with any reasonable request from competent law enforcement agents or representatives, judicial authorities, governmental agencies or bodies, including competent data protection authorities. Your personal data may be transferred upon the personal data administrator's own initiative to the police or the judicial authorities as evidence or if there are justified suspicions of an unlawful act or crime committed by you through your registration with or use of the BioRural Toolkit or other communication with us.

3.5 The personal data administrator may process your personal data for the preservation of the legitimate interests of BioRural project, its partners or a third party if and when your registration with, or use of, the BioRural Toolkit, the Website, Social Media Channels or other communication channels can be considered (a) a violation of any applicable terms of use or the intellectual property rights or any other right of a third party, (b) a threat to the security or integrity of the BioRural Toolkit, (c) a danger to the BioRural Toolkit or any of BioRural project's or its subcontractors' underlying systems due to viruses, Trojan horses, spyware, malware or any other form of malicious code, or (d) in any way hateful, obscene, discriminating, racist, slanderous, spiteful, hurtful or in some other way inappropriate or illegal.

Legal basis for processing: the legal basis for processing will be your consent (Article 6(1)(a) of the Regulation). You may withdraw your consent at any time, without affecting the lawfulness of processing carried out prior to withdrawal.

4. Why is our processing of your personal data legitimate?

4.1 For the processing of your personal data for the purpose outlined in clause 3.1, we ask for your consent.

4.2 The processing of your personal data for the purpose outlined in clause 3.4 is necessary to allow BioRural project to comply with its legal obligations (Article 6(1)(a) of the Regulation).

4.3 The processing of your personal data for the purposes outlined in clauses 3.2, 3.3 and 3.7 is necessary for the purpose of the legitimate interests of BioRural project, which are:

- being able to appropriately respond to your requests for information and other requests;
- communicate your personal data to our partners in the BioRural project to provide you with adequate information;
- allowing us to defend ourselves in legal proceedings;
- continuous improvements to the BioRural Toolkit products and services to ensure that you have the best experience possible;

- keeping our products and services safe from misuse and illegal activity;
- safeguarding our commercial and business interests and needs in light of changing market conditions.
- marketing and promotion of our products, services, brands an overall successful commercialization of our products and services.

4.4 For processing your personal data for the purposes outlined in in clause 3.1, the Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation – State Research Institute in Puławy as the responsible party asks for your consent. By consenting to our processing of your personal data you agree that we are allowed to process your personal data for the purposes and under the conditions outlined in this Privacy Policy.

5. What are our quality assurances?

5.1 IUNG-PIB does its utmost to process only those personal data which are necessary to achieve the purposes listed under the purpose for processing.

5.2 Your personal data is processed only for as long as necessary for the purposes listed above or up until such time where you withdraw your consent for processing them. IUNG-PIB will de-identify your personal data when they are no longer necessary for the purposes outlined in the purpose for processing, unless there is:

- an overriding interest of BioRural project or any other third party in keeping your personal data identifiable;
- a legal or regulatory obligation or a judicial or administrative order that prevents BioRural project from de-identifying them.

5.3 IUNG-PIB takes all the appropriate technical and organizational measures to keep your personal data safe from unauthorized access or theft as well as accidental loss, tampering or destruction. Access by personnel of IUNG-PIB or its third party processors will only be on a need-to-know basis and subject to strict confidentiality obligations.

6. What are your rights?

6.1 You have the right to request access to all personal data processed by IUNG-PIB pertaining to you. IUNG-PIB reserves the right to charge an administrative fee for multiple subsequent requests for access that are clearly submitted for causing nuisance or harm to BioRural project.

6.2 You have the right to ask that any personal data pertaining to you that are inaccurate, are corrected free of charge. If a request for correction is submitted, such request shall be accompanied of proof of the flawed nature of the data for which correction is asked.

6.3 You have the right to withdraw your earlier given consent under clause 4.4 for processing your personal data.

6.4 You have the right to request that personal data pertaining to you will be deleted if they are no longer required in light of the purposes which are outlined above or if you withdraw your consent for processing them. However, you need to keep in mind that a request for deletion will be evaluated by IUNG-PIB against:

- overriding interests of BioRural project or any other third party;
- legal or regulatory obligations or administrative or judicial orders which may contradict such deletion.

Instead of deletion you can also ask that IUNG-PIB limits the processing of your personal data if and when (a) you contest the accuracy of that data, (b) the processing is illegitimate or (c) the data are no longer needed for the purposes which are outlined above, but you need them to defend yourself in judicial proceedings.

6.5 You have the right to oppose the processing of personal data if you are able to prove that there are serious and justified reasons connected with his particular circumstances that warrant such opposition. However, if the intended processing qualifies as direct marketing, you have the right to oppose such processing free of charge and without justification.

6.6 You have the right to receive from us in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format all personal data you have provided us with.

6.7 If you wish to submit a request to exercise one or more of the rights listed above, you can send an e-mail to toolkit@biorural.eu for all data subject rights matters. An e-mail requesting to exercise a right shall not be construed as consent with the processing of your personal data beyond what is required for handling your request.

IUNG-PIB will promptly inform you of having received this request. If the request proves valid, IUNG-PIB shall notify it as soon as reasonably possible and at the latest thirty (30) days after having received the request.

7. Recipients of personal data

The collected personal data may be made available to public authorities or entities entitled to obtain the data on the basis of generally applicable laws, as well as to persons or entities that will participate in the implementation of the BioRural project.

8. Period of personal data processing

Personal data will be processed for the period of time necessary for the aforementioned purposes, for a minimum period of 5 years from the end of the project.

9. Information on automated decision-making and profiling

IUNG-PIB will not use your data for automated decision-making and profiling.

The provision of data by you is voluntary and has no consequences. If you have any complaint regarding the processing of your personal data by IUNG-PIB, you may always contact BioRural project via the e-mail address mentioned in the first paragraph of this clause. If you remain unsatisfied with BioRural project's response, you are free to file a complaint with the competent data protection authority, i.e. the data protection authority of the country where you reside or the Polish President of the Personal Data Protection Office. For more information, visit <https://uodo.gov.pl/en>

8.7 Annex VII. Terms and conditions

Welcome to the BioRural Toolkit!

Please read these Terms and Conditions ("Terms") carefully before using our online tool ("Toolkit"). By accessing or using the Toolkit, you agree to be bound by these Terms.

1. Definitions

- **"Toolkit"** refers to the online tool provided by the Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation (IUNG-PIB).
- **"User"** refers to any person who accesses or uses the Toolkit.
- **"Content"** refers to any information, text, graphics, photos, or other materials uploaded, downloaded, or appearing on the Toolkit.
- **"User Content"** refers to the Content that Users upload or post to the Toolkit.

2. License to Use

IUNG-PIB grants Users open access to the Toolkit, in accordance with these Terms. This access is for personal, non-commercial use only unless otherwise agreed upon in writing.

3. Prohibited Conduct

Regarding the use of the Toolkit, Users agree not to:

- Violate any laws or regulations.
- Infringe on the intellectual property rights.
- Upload or distribute any harmful or malicious content.
- Attempt to interfere with the proper functioning of the Toolkit.
- Use the Toolkit to harass, abuse, or harm others.

4. Right to Terminate Accounts

IUNG-PIB reserves the right to suspend or terminate any account, especially in cases of violations of these Terms or for any other reason deemed necessary.

5. How a User Can Cancel/Terminate an Account

To cancel or terminate an account, Users may do so by accessing their account settings or contacting customer support at mwloga@iung.pulawy.pl. Upon termination, Users' access to the Service will be revoked, and their data may be deleted in accordance with the Privacy Policy.

6. Ownership of Your Content

Users retain ownership of any Content they upload to the Service. However, by uploading Content, Users grant to IUNG-PIB a worldwide, non-exclusive, royalty-free license to use, reproduce, modify, adapt, publish, and display the Content in connection with the Toolkit.

7. User Generated Conte

Users are solely responsible for the Content they create and share on the Service. IUNG-PIB does not endorse, guarantee, or assume responsibility for any User Content. IUNG-PIB does however retain the right to verify the content uploaded to the Toolkit by Users regarding their relevance for the BioRural Toolkit, and compliance with the Terms and conditions.

8. DMCA Section

If you believe that your copyrighted work has been used in a way that constitutes copyright infringement, please notify our designated DMCA agent at toolkit@biorural.eu with the following information:

- A description of the copyrighted work claimed to be infringed.
- A description of the material that is claimed to be infringing.
- Contact information, including an address, telephone number, and email address.
- A statement that you have a good faith belief that the use of the material is not authorized by the copyright owner.
- A statement, under penalty of perjury, that the information provided is accurate and that you are authorized to act on behalf of the copyright owner.

10. Right to Update or Modify Terms

IUNG-PIB reserves the right to modify these Terms at any time. Users will be notified of significant changes and are encouraged to review the Terms periodically. Continued use of the Toolkit after any modifications constitutes acceptance of the updated Terms.

11. Disclaimer of Warranty

The Service is provided "as is" and "as available" without any warranties, express or implied. At the same time, IUNG-PIB does not guarantee the accuracy, completeness, or reliability of the data provided by its Users.

12. Disclaimer of Liability

To the fullest extent permitted by law, IUNG-PIB shall not be liable for any indirect, incidental, special, consequential, or punitive damages arising from the use of or inability to use the Service.

13. Governing Law

These Terms are governed by the laws of the Republic of Poland. Any disputes arising under these Terms will be subject to the exclusive jurisdiction of the courts located in Poland.

In matters not covered by these Terms and Conditions, appropriate provisions prevailing at the territory of the Republic of Poland are applicable, and in particular: the Act of 23 April 1964 – Civil Code, the Act of 30 May 2014 on consumer rights, the Act of 18 July 2002 on electronically supplied services, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).

14. Privacy Policy

Your use of the Service is also governed by our [Privacy Policy](#), which explains how we collect, use, and protect your information. The BioRural project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme (grant agreement No 101060166), complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU Regulation 2016/679).

1. **Data Controller:** The Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation – State Research

Institute in Puławy (IUNG-PIB) is responsible for processing your personal data in connection with the BioRural project. For inquiries, contact iod@iung.pulawy.pl

2. **Data Collection:** We collect data such as name, email, postal address, and more, as specified in our Privacy Policy.
3. **Data Usage:** Personal data is used to provide and improve our Toolkit, communicate with you, and comply with legal obligations.
4. **Data Security:** We implement appropriate measures to protect your data.
5. **User Rights:** You have rights to access, correct, delete, or restrict the processing of your personal data.
6. **Automated Decision-Making:** We do not engage in automated decision-making or profiling.

For any questions or concerns regarding these Terms, please contact us at:

- (1) In writing: Czartoryskich 8, 24-100 Puławy, POLAND
- (2) By email: mwloga@iung.pulawy.pl

The Terms and Conditions are effective as of 1/05/2023.

